

Genetic Tools for Feed-Efficient and Sustainable Meat Production in Latvian Sheep Breeds

Version 1

Description

1. Scientific Excellence

1.1. Background, hypothesis, aim.

Livestock production involves many global sustainability issues: animal health and welfare, greenhouse gas emissions, use of natural resources, food safety and public health, and production efficiency. Breeders can positively contribute to these challenges, by including them in their breeding programs (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Fao)). Innovative strategies to improve sheep production efficiency can have a significant impact on the sustainability, resilience, and overall success of the livestock industry.

This proposal argues in support of the need for sustainable use of native animal genetic resources in sheep husbandry. In our study, we address genetic improvement related to production efficiency, particularly through the selection for breeding the most feed-efficient of animals in the Latvian native sheep breed. This project proposal addresses key challenges: maintaining genetic diversity, increasing environmental sustainability, and increasing product efficiency in the sheep industry.

1. Livestock production involves the use of natural resources such as water and feed and is associated with environmental emissions such as greenhouse gases and manure.

The challenge of feeding a growing population requires an increase in agricultural productivity by 70% by 2050 [1]. We are at a critical juncture where food systems must balance the need for sufficient, healthy, and affordable food with the need to preserve ecosystems essential to life [1]. Therefore, the use of natural resources for livestock production is one of the major aspects causing stress on the environment. To solve this

problem, new technologies are needed to increase production while ensuring environmental sustainability. The goal is to produce food more economically and environmentally efficiently than current practices.

Feed costs are high due to poor grain-growing conditions in major grain-producing countries, the use of feed grains in ethanol production, and increased competition for land for crop production relative to urban development [2]. **Feed efficiency (FE)** in growing lambs (i.e. the animal's ability to reach a market or adult body weight (BW) with the least amount of feed intake), is a key factor in the sheep industry. Improving FE reduces production costs. Given that feed costs account for more than two-thirds of total meat production costs, reducing them can have huge profit margins for the manufacturer [3]. The results indicate that the selection of FE in sheep could reduce feed consumption without affecting the growth performance of sheep [4].

In addition to management methods that optimise productive efficiency, it is important to select more genetically efficient sheep. Efficient animals that require fewer natural resources, are more environmentally friendly and economically viable [5]. Thus, there is a need to develop innovative approaches for optimal use of existing genetic variations both between and within animal populations. Traditionally, meat breeding programs have focused on outputs, due mainly to the routine availability of phenotypic data on outputs or correlated traits.

Marker-assisted selection (MAS) offers a valuable tool for identifying desirable traits, including carcass composition characteristics. Assessing carcass characteristics can be challenging, as it often requires post-feeding measurements [6]. To overcome this challenge, MAS relies on established relationships between DNA regions and specific quantitative trait loci (QTL) within a breed [6]. The SheepQTLdb database (December 2023, <https://bioregistry.io/registry/sheepqtlpdb>) contains limited QTL information for sheep breeds, hindering its direct use in MAS. Nonetheless, assessing the variability of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in local sheep breeds holds promise for selective breeding efforts [7]. Studies have identified the period from weaning to six months of age as critical for maximising lamb growth rates [8]. This phase presents an opportunity to identify animals suitable for breeding purposes or meat production. MAS can be strategically employed in two ways [9]. Firstly, it can assist in selecting crossbred offspring with desired genetic profiles and estimated breeding values (EBVs) for carcass quality traits, optimising crossbreeding outcomes. Second, analysing the genetic markers of

already-born lambs enables the prediction of their productive potential, aiding decisions about their inclusion in breeding programs [10,11].

Genome-wide sequencing methodologies (GWAS, genome-wide association studies) are used to find specific QTL traits related to productive characteristics in the sheep genome. Two full and 12 partial genome scans have reported QTL for meat productivity on chromosomes 1-6, 8, 18, 20, 21, and 24 in populations of Coopworth, Scottish Blackface, British Texel, Charollais, Suffolk, and Texel sheep [12, 13, 14, 15]. Therefore, genetic variations found in specific QTL regions in association with sheep productive traits can be used as molecular markers for MAS selection for sheep breeding. At present, two DNA tests (LoinMax and MyoMax) [16] are commercially available for genetic variants in the Carwell and Myostatin genes [17].

The current project involves conducting a sequencing study of the sheep genome of Latvian sheep breeds using the Sheep Industries OvineSNP50 chip developed by Illumina, which offers comprehensive whole-genome coverage with 54,977 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). This advanced sequencing methodology will enable researchers to obtain detailed genetic information (a dataset of genetic variations) from the samples, allowing for in-depth analysis of the genetic background present within the Latvian sheep breeds under study. Currently, feed efficiency-related traits are not commonly included in sheep genetic breeding programs, but their importance in profitability and marketability is increasingly recognised [18]. Efforts are underway to develop efficient and cost-effective measurement methods for integration into breeding programs. Several factors are the undoubted advantage of using a genomic approach to improve FE quality: minimal requirement for expensive measurement (phenotyping) of traits after validation; reduced generation interval (breeding stock can be selected using DNA sampling at a very young age); increased rates of genetic gain [18].

2. Animal genetic resources are part of the biological diversity of the planet. Their genetic variation is being threatened because of the increasing intensification of animal production.

General trends of agricultural development imply an increasing uniformity of animal genetic resources, caused by the loss of endangered breeds and increased inbreeding within commercial breeding populations. Much genetic variation among domestic animal species is being eliminated through breed replacement and crossbreeding [19]. Many local sheep breeds in the Baltic region have special adaptive traits, such as disease resistance, climatic tolerance, and the ability to digest low-quality feed. Although difficult

to quantify, it is likely that they also have an excellent ability to convert limited and poor-quality feed into protein [20,21].

There is a lack of scientific, economic, and genetic evaluation of pure-bred local breeds in different environments. In the future, due to changing livestock production conditions, the genetic variations that exist in these breeds may be indispensable. Therefore, the main object of the current study will be the native Latvian Dark-Head sheep breed, which makes up about 23% of the total sheep population and 70% of pure breeds and is the only sheep breed of local origin bred in Latvia. This native breed (LT; Latvijas tumšgalve) originated between 1927 and 1937 in Latvia by importing Oxford Down and Shropshire sheep from England and crossing them with indigenous coarse-wooled sheep [22]. It was previously established that the LT sheep breed has good productivity, safety of lambs, and milk production. This breed has such positive qualities as fast growth, and a long and wide body, which positively correlates with the back muscles. The amount of amino acids and a better assessment of the taste of meat were found in the muscle tissue of LT sheep. However, in further breeding work, the need to improve the feed efficiency-related parameters was emphasised [23,24].

According to the results of our study on Latvian sheep (LZP Nr. Izp-2021/1-0489, 2022-2024), a significant difference was established in individual lambs from the same herd in terms of indicators characterizing the FE trait [25]. The Latvian Dark-Head breed has a feed conversion ratio (FCR) ranging from 3.33 to 7.92, averaging 5.09 ± 0.15 kg. For low-productive lambs, the average daily gain is 261.29 ± 39.99 g, while for highly productive lambs it is 415.77 ± 42.55 g. We found that the IOFC (income from meat sales over the cost of concentrated feed) for high-producing animals was on average €16.31 higher than for low-producing animals [25].

Thus, considering the economic benefits of breeding effective animals in sheep farming, the need to develop the current topic in a wider area becomes obvious.

Therefore, the purpose of our current study is to identify a panel of molecular markers associated with productive FE-related characteristics in sheep of other meat sheep breeds in Latvia: Ile de France, Charolais, Texel, Suffolk, Dorper, and Oxford Down. Subsequently, this panel of molecular markers is intended to be introduced into the local Latvian Dark-Head sheep breed through genetic selection (MAS), providing an unconventional approach to improving productive qualities without introducing genetic material from outside (crossbreeding).

Currently, no molecular markers for performance and feed efficiency-related favourable characteristics are available for Latvian sheep breeds as well as for other native breeds in the Baltic region. The physiological determinants of FE-related traits or putative biomarkers used to analyse animal-to-animal variation in live lambs could be used as a cost-effective and rapid tool for genetic selection or management decisions. By improving native agricultural genetics without introducing external genetic material through crossbreeding, we aim to enhance the intrinsic qualities of these breeds.

The objective of this study is to determine if molecular markers were previously associated with FE-related characteristics in a training population of Latvian lambs when fed the same diet and can accurately predict these traits in LT sheep breeds. Novelty: we set out to develop an effective method for determining markers of FE-related traits based on molecular markers obtained from the blood of live lambs.

In addition, we believe that through the identification and selection of specific molecular markers, this project will pave the way for more sustainable and efficient sheep farming practices in the Baltic region, as our goal is also to increase cooperation between the Baltic countries and attract new partners to promote comprehensive research into sheep farming practices in the region. By working collaboratively and sharing our findings, we can contribute to the advancement of sheep breeding and promote the conservation of local sheep breeds for future generations.

To achieve our aim, we will use our multidisciplinary expertise in molecular biology, genetics, agriculture, and biotechnology, as well as unrestricted access to samples of lambs in feeding trials—peripheral blood, phenotyping, and FE-related parameters.

Animals with predicted performance associated with the main economic pathways (Feed efficiency traits) can be used for further breeding, thus providing synergy between the two topics: LZP Nr. lzp-2021/1-0489, (2022-2024), related to our pilot study, and LZP Nr. lzp-2024/1-0092, current proposal.

Continued research in this area is critical due to the significant results already obtained and the potential for further development. The LZP project No. lzp-2021/1-0489 has yielded valuable insights into molecular markers related to mitochondrial biogenesis and associated with favourable FE-related parameters in Latvian sheep breeds. Expanding our research builds upon past successes, ensuring sustained impact on sheep farming

practices. We aim to refine initial findings, providing reliable molecular markers for practical use. Addressing knowledge gaps in sheep genetics, our future research will enhance understanding and contribute to developing sustainable farming practices amidst evolving agricultural and environmental challenges.

Specific objectives of the project to achieve the aim will be as follows:

Objective 1. To characterise phenotypic parameters in live animals (control of live weight and measuring the average daily gain (ADG), depth of muscle, and adipose tissue using ultrasound) and FE-related parameters. Evaluate the total post-fat cohort of lambs by the highest, average, and lowest values of the FE-related parameters (Feeding Trial I, data from Feeding Trial 0).

Objective 2. Scan the genetic background in DNA collections of lambs from Latvian sheep breeds using sequencing methodology, Sheep Industries OvineSNP50 chip (Illumina Inc. (California, USA)).

Objective 3. Analyse the association between the value of the above phenotypic and FE-related characteristics (Objective 1) and genetic variations (Objective 2). Develop a panel of molecular markers associated with the FE-related parameters.

Objective 4. Validate a panel of molecular markers associated with the highest, average, and lowest values of the FE-related parameters in a secondary collection of animals (Feeding trial II), using Predictive modeling with biostatistical methods (regression analysis, tree/forest modelling).

Funder

Latvian council of Science

Grant

Genetic Tools for Feed-Efficient

and Sustainable Meat
Production in Latvian Sheep
Breeds (Izp-2024/1-0092)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Genetic Tools for Feed-Efficient and Sustainable Meat Production in Latvian Sheep Breeds

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian council of Science](#)

Grants: Genetic Tools for Feed-Efficient and Sustainable Meat Production in Latvian Sheep Breeds (Izp-2024/1-0092)

Project: Genetic Tools for Feed-Efficient and Sustainable Meat Production in Latvian Sheep Breeds (Izp-2024/1-0092)

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

2_Database of identification and fattening indicators of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025).

Data on lamb samples of the year 2025 (the 1st year of project), or A25 group, which consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs during the beginning and end of fattening, intensive fattening data (real and calculated on the 90th and 150th days), the amount of feed used.

Based on the requirements of the breeding program of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there

were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with previous years from the lzp-2021/1-0489 project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening (currently there is data for 2022 - 2024) and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

10_Database of all DNA loci or SNP genotypes in the SNP chip of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 2nd year of the project (Feed trial 2; 2026).

The GWAS will result in a database containing information on more than 54K DNA loci, of which only a small fraction could be QTL or related to feed efficiency (Fe) indicators. By performing a statistical or association analysis between Feed efficiency parameters and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the Fe indicators. The significant loci will be identified in association analysis and will be copied into the 5th database.

Accordingly, it will be necessary to create a database containing information only on specific SNPs in all intensively fattened lambs analyzed, so that using this specific database, machine learning algorithms can be developed for the determination of estimated breeding values (EBVs) or the use of MAS.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical significance of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

It will be necessary to create a database containing information on specific SNPs genotyped in the second trial group.

A database with information only on specific SNPs will be used to validate (1) the statistical association of loci found in the first phase of the project and (2) the use of common molecular marker panels using these to determine estimated breeding values (EBV) or use them in MAS.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Association analyze data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previous years' intensive fattening data was used as the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

It is not possible to use data from analyses of other breeds/populations, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-11-19

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

11_Database of previously significant 57 SNP genotypes of DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened within the framework of the project

As a result of the LZP-2021/1-0489 project, 57 DNA loci or SNPs were discovered that were found to be statistically significantly associated with feed efficiency indicators. The specific loci were genotyped in all LZP-2021/1-0489 project samples and are being used in further research to improve the reliability of the obtained data.

In the database, SNPs are coded with a laboratory code and an rs ID number. The gene in which the SNP is located is also indicated. The genotypes of each SNP are presented using standard IUB/IUPAC nucleic acid codes, representing the genotype of two alleles at a single locus with a single letter.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The significant loci discovered in the previous project are genotyped in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs from the current project. The obtained results are compiled in a database so that they can be used in previously developed machine learning algorithms and make improvements/precisions in the prediction process.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

As well as previous years' intensive fattening data was used as the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

It is also not possible to use data from analyses of other breeds/populations, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-11-19

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

1_Database of DNA loci or SNP genotyping results on the SNP chip of DNA samples of sheep breeds and intensively fattened lambs (Group 0) raised in Latvia, created before the project.

DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs generated within the previous Izp-2021/1-0489 project will be subjected to a full genome SNP analysis, which includes genotyping of approximately 54k SNPs. The obtained data on locus genotypes will be compiled in a database so that they can be used in association analysis related to feed efficiency and their QTL identification in the Latvian sheep population and individually in the Latvian Dark-head breed.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The collection of WGS data in a database will create the opportunity to use them both in association analysis in a specific project and in future projects, and to use them in other studies, for example, comparing them with information available in the public domain - for other breeds.

The existence of the database will also create the opportunity to transfer these data to scientific databases.

By collecting genotypic data from intensive fattening, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a specific year and compare their data with data from other years and with data from other breeds.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as WGS analysis of 54k SNP genotypes has not been performed on samples from the Latvian sheep population. Also, the aim of the study is to analyze samples of intensively matured lambs and samples of sheep raised in Latvia, which are also not available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

3_Database of calculated feed efficiency indicators of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025).

Data on lamb samples of the year 2025 (the 1st year of project), or A25 group, which consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

Feed efficiency (Fe) in growing lambs (i.e. the animal's ability to reach a market or adult body weight (BW) with the least amount of feed intake), is a key factor in the sheep industry. Improving Fe reduces production costs. Given that feed costs account for more than two-thirds of total meat production costs, reducing them can have huge profit margins for the manufacturer. The results indicate that the selection of Fe in sheep could reduce feed consumption without affecting the growth performance of sheep.

The dataset includes data on feed efficiency indicators: (1) ratio traits: Feed efficiency (FE), Feed conversion ratio (FCR), Relative growth rate (RGR), Kleiber's ratio (KR), or (2) regression or residual traits: Residual feed intake (RFI), Residual weight gain (RWG) and Residual intake and body weight gain (RIG). Calculations were made by using formulas from Lima et al., 2017.

Based on the requirements of the breeding program of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to

estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of Feed efficiency of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with other year date.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained and calculated data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening (currently there is data for 2022 - 2024) and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-24

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

4_Database of DNA loci or SNP genotyping results of DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025).

DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs intensively fattened in the first year of the project (2025; A25) will be subjected to a full genome SNP analysis, which includes genotyping of approximately 54k SNPs. The obtained data on locus genotypes will be compiled in a database so that they can be used in association analysis related to feed efficiency and their QTL identification in the Latvian sheep population and individually in the Latvian Dark-head breed.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The collection of WGS data in a database will create the opportunity to use them both in association analysis in a specific project and in future projects, and to use them in other studies, for example, comparing them with information available in the public domain - for other breeds.

The existence of the database will also create the opportunity to transfer these data to scientific databases.

By collecting genotypic data from intensive fattening, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a specific year and compare their data with data from other years and with data from other breeds.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening (currently there is data for 2022 - 2024) and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-29

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

5_Database of association analysis results of DNA loci or SNP genotyped in the SNP chip with feed efficiency indicators

Genome-wide sequencing methodologies (GWAS, Genome-wide association studies) are used to find specific QTL traits, related to productive characteristics in sheep genome. Genetic variations found in specific QTL regions in association with sheep productive traits can be used as molecular markers for MAS (Marker-assisted selection) selection for sheep breeding.

MAS relies on established relationships between DNA regions and specific quantitative trait loci (QTL) within a breed. Marker-assisted selection offers a valuable tool for identifying desirable traits. Firstly, it can assist in selecting crossbred offspring with desired genetic profiles and estimated breeding values (EBVs) for carcass quality traits, optimising crossbreeding outcomes. Second, analysing the genetic markers of already-born lambs enables the prediction of their productive potential, aiding decisions about their inclusion in breeding programs.

Analyse the association between the value of the above phenotypic and FE-related characteristics and genetic variations. Develop a panel of molecular markers associated with the FE-related parameters.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

By performing a statistical or association analysis between Feed efficiency parameters and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the Fe indicators. The results will include both information about a

possible QTL region in the sheep genome and a statistically reliable association between a specific SNP and the Fe trait.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical reliability of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

The information contained in the database will be used for further studies: (1) to develop a manual genotyping method; (2) to validate the obtained association in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs in 2020; (3) to develop know-how and provide recommendations for sheep farmers.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Process produced data
- Other

Association analyze data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as WGS analysis of 54k SNP genotypes has not been performed on samples from the Latvian sheep population.

It is also not possible to use data from analyses of other breeds/populations, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-29

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

6_Database of statistically significant or associated with feed efficiency SNP genotyping results of DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025).

The GWAS will result in a database containing information on more than 54K DNA loci, of which only a small fraction could be QTL or related to feed efficiency (Fe) indicators. By performing a statistical or association analysis between Feed efficiency parameters and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the Fe indicators. The significant loci will be identified in association analysis and will be copied into the 5th database.

Accordingly, it will be necessary to create a database containing information only on specific SNPs in all intensively fattened lambs analyzed, so that using this specific database, machine learning algorithms can be developed for the determination of estimated breeding values (EBVs) or the use of MAS.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical significance of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

The information contained in the database will be used for further studies: (1) to develop a manual genotyping method; (2) to validate the obtained association in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs in 2026; (3) to develop know-how and provide recommendations for sheep farmers.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Accordingly, it will be necessary to create a database containing information only on specific SNPs in all intensively fattened lambs analyzed, so that using this specific database, machine learning algorithms can be developed for the determination of estimated breeding values (EBVs) or the use of MAS.

The information contained in the database will be used for further studies: (1) to develop a manual genotyping method; (2) to validate the obtained association in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs in 2020; (3) to develop know-how and provide recommendations for sheep farmers.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Experimental data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Association analyze data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as WGS analysis of 54k SNP genotypes has not been performed on samples from the Latvian sheep population.

It is also not possible to use data from analyses of other breeds/populations, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-23

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

7_Database of identification and fattening indicators of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 2nd year of the project (Feed trial 2; 2026).

Data on lamb samples of the year 2026 (the 2nd year of the project), or A26 group, which consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs during the beginning and end of fattening, intensive fattening data (real and calculated on the 90th and 150th days), the amount of feed used.

Based on the requirements of the breeding program of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with previous and next years

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

As well as previous years' intensive fattening data, it was used as the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zotero

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-16

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

8_Database of calculated feed efficiency indicators of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 2nd year of the project (Feed trial 2; 2026).

Data on lamb samples of the year 2026 (the 2nd year of project), or A26 group, which consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

Feed efficiency (Fe) in growing lambs (i.e. the animal's ability to reach a market or adult body weight (BW) with the least amount of feed intake), is a key factor in the sheep industry. Improving Fe reduces production costs. Given that feed costs account for more than two-thirds of total meat production costs, reducing them can have huge profit margins for the manufacturer. The results indicate that the selection of Fe in sheep could reduce feed consumption without affecting the growth performance of sheep.

The dataset includes data on feed efficiency indicators: (1) ratio traits: Feed efficiency (FE), Feed conversion ratio (FCR), Relative growth rate (RGR), Kleiber's ratio (KR), or (2) regression or residual traits: Residual feed intake (RFI), Residual weight gain (RWG) and Residual intake and body weight gain (RIG). Calculations were made by using formulas from Lima et al., 2017.

Based on the requirements of the breeding program of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of Feed efficiency of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with other year date.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained and calculated data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

As well as previous years' intensive fattening data, it was used as the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-30

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

9_Database of statistically significant or feed efficiency-associated SNP genotyping results of DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 2nd year of the project (Feed trial 2; 2026).

The GWAS will result in a database containing information on more than 54K DNA loci, of which only a small fraction could be QTL or related to feed efficiency (Fe) indicators. By performing a statistical or association analysis between Feed efficiency parameters and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the Fe indicators. The significant loci will be identified in the association analysis and will be copied into the 5th database.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical significance of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

The selected SNPs or DNA loci will be genotyped in DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs from the second year of the project, thus creating a database that will compile the genotyping results of each lamb sample.

A database with information only on specific SNPs will be used to validate (1) the statistical association of loci found in the first phase of the project and (2) the use of common molecular marker panels using these to determine estimated breeding values (EBV) or use them in MAS.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The selected SNPs or DNA loci will be genotyped in DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs from the second year of the project, thus creating a database that will compile the genotyping results of each lamb sample.

A database with information only on specific SNPs will be used to validate (1) the statistical association of loci found in the first phase of the project and (2) the use of common molecular marker panels using these to determine estimated breeding values (EBV) or use them in MAS.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Experimental data
- Process produced data
- Other

Association analyze data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as previous years' intensive fattening data was used as the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

It is also not possible to use data from analyses of other breeds/populations, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available upon contact with the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and know-how preparation. Also, the database will contain unique information.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

P1_Database of identification and fattening indicators of sheep breeds and intensively fattened lambs (Group or feed trial 0) raised in Latvia, created before the project.

Project of The Latvian Council of Science (LCS) - LZP-2021/1-0489 project: "Development of an innovative approach to identify biological determinants involved in the between-animal variation in feed efficiency in sheep farming."

LZP-2021/1-0489 project data on lamb samples of the year 2022, or A22 group, which consists of 76 intensively fattened lambs from six breeds and nine samples from the LT breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

Based on the requirements of the breeding program of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed before inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with the Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs during the beginning and end of fattening, intensive fattening data—real and calculated on the 90th and 150th day, the amount of feed used, and slaughter data. Ultrasonography data were used to calculate muscle and/or fat depth changes at the 13th rib during the fattening period.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with other years.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

id: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8143154>, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

P2_Calculated feed efficiency indicators of sheep breeds and intensively fattened lambs (Group or feed trial 0) raised in Latvia, created before the project.

LZP-2021/1-0489 project data on lamb samples of the year 2022, or the A22 group, and year 2023, which consists of 76 + 92 intensively fattened lambs from eighth breeds.

The dataset includes data on feed efficiency indicators: (1) ratio traits: Feed efficiency (FE), Feed conversion ratio (FCR), Relative growth rate (RGR), Kleiber's ratio (KR), or (2) regression or residual traits: Residual feed intake (RFI), Residual weight gain (RWG) and Residual intake and body weight gain (RIG). Calculations were made by using formulas from Lima et al., 2017 (<https://doi.org/10.1590/S1806-92902017001000005>).

Based on the requirements of the breeding program of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analyzed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets or quadruplets from different ewes and health status was assessed before inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with other year date

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

id: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14222853>, Type: doi

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The databases will be available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

P3_Database of previously significant 57 SNP genotypes of DNA samples of sheep breeds and intensively fattened lambs created before the project.

LZP-2021/1-0489 project data on lamb samples of the year 2022, or the A22 group, and year 2023, or th A23, which consists of 76 + 92 intensively fattened lambs from eighth breeds.

The database contains genotyping results for 57 SNPs, for which a statistically significant association with one of the feed efficiency indicators was established within the project, using NGS methodology and association statistical methods. The specific SNPs were selected for further work as the first DNA molecular markers for future sheep breeding programs in Latvia.

In the database, SNPs are coded with a laboratory code and an rs ID number. The gene in which the SNP is located is also indicated. The genotypes of each SNP are presented using standard IUB/IUPAC nucleic acid codes, representing the genotype of two alleles at a single locus with a single letter.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Genotypic characteristics of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to feed efficiency and other fattening characteristics.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

id: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14224369>, Type: doi

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists for more analysis on other type of breeds in different populations.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

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Comment:

The data will become open data after full data publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

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3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

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3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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